

***In situ* MgCr₂O₄ spinel precursor for consolidation of pure α -Al₂O₃ compacts**

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Abstract : Densification behaviour of α -Al₂O₃ has been studied in presence of *in situ* microfine MgCr₂O₄ spinel precursor derived from co-precipitated 1 : 1 MgO.Cr₂O₃ hydrogel. The mixed hydroxides hydrogel was synthesized by aqueous phase interaction of Mg²⁺ and Cr³⁺ ions using dilute NH₄OH as basic medium. The dried hydrogel on heat treatment at 500 °C transformed into MgO.Cr₂O₃ spinel as evidenced by XRD studies. α -Al₂O₃ compacts containing spinel precursor from 0.5 to 1.5% were fabricated by uniaxial pressing and fired at different temperatures (1450–1550 °C) with a fixed soaking period of 2 h. The degree of sintering was evaluated by assessing physical properties like volume shrinkage, apparent porosity (AP), bulk density (BD) and cold crushing strength (CCS) of the fired compacts. The phase composition and the micro structural features of the fired samples were determined by XRD and SEM techniques respectively.

The minor presence of *in situ* MgCr₂O₄ spinel derived from the co-precipitated hydrogel (1.0% w/w) to alumina was observed to exhibit profound mineralizing action on densification of α -Al₂O₃ with the development of excellent mechanical properties and dense microstructure of α -Al₂O₃-spinel composite at the sintering temperature as low as 1550 °C.

Keywords : MgCr₂O₄ precursor, consolidation, alumina-magchrome composites.

Introduction

Because of excellent combination of thermo-mechanical and mechano-chemical properties, direct bonded or spinel bonded high purity alumina ceramics have been emerged as one of the prime structural ceramics materials. It finds multifarious industrial applications like electronics, engineering components, grinding media, abrasives, catalyst carriers, membranes and electrical insulators etc. Though ultrapure alumina has made tremendous contributions to the advancement of contemporary material research, technological processing of high purity alumina becomes complicated due to formation of liquid phases at the grain boundary out of minor impurities present in the starting powder, existence of micro pores due to agglomeration of starting powder and improper packing during fabrication. This requires a very high temperature (1700 °C) for its effective densification demanding the use of prospective sintering aid for alumina system in order to attain the proper sinterability with desired characteristics at a lower temperature of firing.

The effect of original boehmite structure and magnesia doping on the phase transformation of transitional alumina and α -Al₂O₃ densification was investigated by Radonjic and co-workers¹. Magnesia doping plays an important role in the processing of gel dried alumina. The phase equilibria in the alumina-chrome refractory oxides system showed a complete solid solution series with no compound formation although there exists a miscibility gap in the solid solution series between two oxides below 925 °C².

Hirata *et al.*³ studied sintering behavior of Cr₂O₃-Al₂O₃ system and measured the activation energy of sintering reaction as 102 kJ/mol which is almost equal to the activation energy of diffusion of Al ion in Al₂O₃ single crystal, therefore diffusion of cation is believed to control the sintering behavior of this material. The addition of TiO₂ has accelerated the sintering behavior due to enhancement of diffusion of the cation.

Prasad *et al.*⁴ investigated solid state sintering behavior of MgO.Al₂O₃ and Cr₂O₃ system between 1450–1650

°C using different combination of $\text{MgO} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and Cr_2O_3 . They reported that the crystalline phases present in the sintered body are mainly Mg-Al and Mg-Cr spinel with a closely packed microstructure of rounded and polygonal spinel grains.

Parya *et al.*⁵ studied the effect of ZnAl_2O_4 spinel precursor as sintering aid for pure alumina system. Enhanced densification of alumina bodies with dense microstructure has been occurred by minor incorporation of 0.2% ZnAl_2O_4 spinel precursor during sintering at 1500 °C. This spinel precursor has been observed to act as a grain growth inhibitor for pure alumina system.

Active ultra fine MgCr_2O_4 precursor synthesised by either co-precipitation route or sol-gel route which by the virtue of high purity, homogeneity, large surface area, considerable structural defects, can function as useful sintering aid for pure alumina system. The synthesis and characterisation of ultrafine MgCr_2O_4 precursor through co-precipitation route using different basic media has already been reported⁶.

The objective of present investigation is to study the influence of *in situ* formed MgCr_2O_4 spinel precursor on the densification behavior and microstructural aspects of pure alumina system during firing at lower temperatures (1450 to 1550 °C). Since large addition of spinel precursor may adversely affect the final product characteristics, the addition of it to α -alumina has been kept restricted to a lower range.

Results and discussion

Physicochemical characteristics of α -alumina powder and dried spinel precursor are : Al_2O_3 (%), 99.70; Na_2O (%), 0.25; SiO_2 (%), trace; LOI (%), 0.03; average particle diameter, 1.01 μm ; sp. surface area, 5.1 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$; crystalline variety, α -alumina.

Molar ratio of $\text{MgO} : \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$, 1 : 1; solid content (%), 40.2; loose bulk density, 0.40 g cm^{-3} ; DTA peak temperatures (Endo, °C), 277 and 404; BET specific surface area, 197 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$; average particle diameter, 0.301 μm (spherical); crystalline phases, heat treated at 500 °C, MgCr_2O_4 spinel; crystallinity, poorly crystalline; IR absorption peak at 800 °C, 645, 535 and 427 cm^{-1} .

Intense IR bands at 645 cm^{-1} , 535 cm^{-1} , 427 cm^{-1} of mixed hydrogel when calcined at 800 °C may be due to

complex interaction of coupled stretching and bending vibrations and out of plane coupled bending vibration of defective spinel structure containing Mg-O and Cr-O bonds.

XRD patterns of mixed hydroxides hydrogel of magnesium and chromium dried at 110 °C and heat treated at 500 °C has been given in Fig. 1 which clearly indicate the amorphous behavior of the hydrogel powder at 110 °C but transformed into poorly crystalline MgCr_2O_4 spinel on heat treatment at 500 °C.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of the spinel precursor powders dried at 110 °C (MCH-1) and heat treated at 500 °C (MC-15).

The temperature of firing for pressed alumina compacts were selected in the lower range of 1550 °C considering the greater reactivity of *in situ* formed MgCr_2O_4 spinel. After drying, hydrogel containing samples showed sufficient green strength (around 10 MPa) suitable for easy handling. The samples were fired in neutral atmosphere due to presence of redox system in the composition.

The fired color of the hydrogel containing compact was pink without formation of any crack or visible defect. The magnitude of densification was studied by measurement of volume shrinkage, apparent porosity, bulk density and cold crushing strength of the fired sample. The variation of these properties against additive contents and firing temperature graphically represented in Figs. 2 to 5.

Fig. 2. Variation of volume shrinkage (%) of Al₂O₃-MgCr₂O₄ compacts on firing.

Fig. 5. Variation of cold crushing strength (MPa) of Al₂O₃-MgCr₂O₄ compacts on firing.

Fig. 3. Variation of apparent porosity (%) of Al₂O₃-MgCr₂O₄ compacts on firing.

Fig. 4. Variation of bulk density (g cm⁻³) of Al₂O₃-MgCr₂O₄ compacts on firing.

Volume shrinkage :

From Fig. 2 it is quite evident that the firing shrinkage of the spinel containing samples increases continuously at a faster rate up to highest temperature of firing (1550 °C) indicating rapid elimination of pores caused by enhanced material interaction and transportation through diffusion. Maximum shrinkage (13.8%) is observed for 1.0% addition of mixed hydrogel during firing at 1550 °C. However, shrinkage values are well within the limit to cause any defect or distortion in the fired body.

Apparent porosity :

It is observed from Fig. 3 that in case of spinel precursor, the apparent porosity reduces significantly showing an inflexion at 1500 °C and reaches below 1.0% at 1550 °C. More or less 100% densified alumina products are derived from 1.0% addition of spinel precursor at 1550 °C. This may be attributed to the mineralising action of *in situ* reactive MgCr₂O₄ spinel towards Al₂O₃-Cr₂O₃ solid solution and better interlocking of the crystalline phases formed. This was verified from the higher values of apparent porosity exhibited by the dopant free compacts at all firing temperatures. The tendency of showing increased porosity in excess of 1.0% addition of spinel to Al₂O₃ body may be probably due to formation of a non compatible secondary phase.

Bulk density :

Bulk density results of sintered products correlated the magnitude of densification to the great extent as evident from Fig. 4. It highlights the rapid rate of increase of BD values up to 1550 °C followed by moderate increase at 1550 °C in spinel containing alumina compacts. BD value (3.85 g cm^{-3}) of α -alumina compacts containing 1.0% spinel precursor on firing at 1550 °C is observed approaching closely to the theoretical density of α -alumina (3.95 g cm^{-3}). The reduction of bulk density values for 1.5% spinel containing alumina bodies during all temperature of firing may be caused by the separation of phases at the grain boundary.

Cold crushing strength :

Fig. 5 demonstrated that with spinel precursor as dopant and increasing firing temperature up to 1550 °C, the sintered α -alumina products exhibits very high compressive values indicating better bonding in α -alumina compacts. Maximum strength (686.7 MPa) was exhibited by α -alumina compacts containing 1.0% spinel precursor at 1550 °C. However, slight reduction of compressive strength values with sintered alumina body containing

1.5% spinel may be attributed to the strain in the crystal lattices causing lack of the direct bonding between the grains.

Thus, achievement of highest BD, maximum strength and porosity below 1.0% with spinel added compacts during sintering at 1550 °C indicates excellent sintering action of the spinel.

XRD analysis :

XRD patterns of α -alumina compacts sintered at 1550 °C with and without the presence of spinel precursor exhibited in Figs. 6a and 6b. Fig. 6a reveals that sintered alumina compacts consist of stable corundum as only one crystalline phase while spinel precursor containing sinter compacts. Fig. 6b exhibited corundum as major crystalline phase along with MgCr_2O_4 as minor phase. However, peak positions of corundum coincide with those of MgCr_2O_4 spinel. Higher intensity counts of the sharp peaks in case of spinel containing bodies than that of spinel precursor free compacts reveal profound mineralizing action of reactive spinel precursor to the formation of solid solution between Al_2O_3 and MgCr_2O_4 leading to the generation of composites.

Fig. 6a. XRD patterns of α -alumina compacts sintered at 1550 °C without spinel precursor.

Fig. 6b. XRD patterns of α-alumina compacts sintered at 1550 °C with 1.0% spinel precursor

SEM analysis

SEM micrographs of α-alumina compacts sintered at 1550 °C with or without the presence of dopant are shown in Figs. 7 and 8. Comparing the microstructure, it is quite evident that reactive spinel precursor favors the formation and even distribution of sub-rounded microfine α-alumina crystals with grain sizes below 1.0 micrometer (Fig. 8). They are uniformly distributed to the forma-

Fig. 7. SEM micrograph of fractured surface of α-alumina fired at 1550 °C without additive

Fig. 8. SEM micrograph of fractured surface of α-alumina compacts fired at 1550 °C with 1.0% MgCr₂O₄ spinel precursor

tion of interlocked α-alumina-spinel compacts during sintering at relatively lower temperature (1550 °C). But a number of entrapped pores and development of large acicular grains with size above 1.0 micrometer has been noticed in the undoped specimen (Fig. 7). The simultaneous occurrence of enhanced grain boundary diffusion amongst phases and rapid pores movement during inter-

action with reactive spinel mineraliser appears to be the most contributing factor in the densification of α -alumina compacts where MgCr_2O_4 spinel functions as grain growth inhibitor for the alumina system.

Experimental

The starting materials for the present study were pure reactive alumina powder (ALCOA, 99.7% Al_2O_3) as matrix and co-precipitated MgCr_2O_4 spinel precursor as dopant. The mixed hydroxides gel of $\text{MgO-Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ system in the molar ratio of 1 : 1 was synthesised by aqueous phase interaction of requisite amount of 0.1 M salt solutions of Mg^{2+} and Cr^{3+} ions at 60 °C and at pH 8.5 using 1 : 1 ammonium hydroxide as basic medium for co-precipitation⁶. The microfine mixed hydroxides hydrogel thus prepared was filtered under suction, washed with hot water to remove impurities and vacuum dried at 80 °C. The vacuum dried powder of mixed hydroxides was then characterized in terms of $\text{MgO} : \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ molar ratio, surface area, thermal and crystallographic properties.

The MgCr_2O_4 spinel precursor calcined at 500 °C was added to the alumina powder in the proportion of 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5% (w/w) respectively. Each batch was thoroughly mixed with 2.5% (w/w) moisture and hydraulically pressed into 2.0 cm diameter by 2.0 cm height cylindrical discs at a pressure of 156.9 MPa. Al_2O_3 compact without any additive was also prepared following the same procedure for comparative study. All the samples were dried at 110 °C and subjected to heat treatment at different temperatures from 1450 to 1550 °C with constant soaking period of 2 h in an electrically operated programmable furnace. The extent of densification was evaluated by measurement of different physical properties of the fired compacts. Volume shrinkage, bulk density, appa-

rent porosity and cold crushing strength were measured following standard methods (ASTM C133-94 and C20-00). The crystalline phase analysis of the powdered sample was carried out by Philips diffractometer PW-1730 instrument, using Ni filtered Cu-K α radiations at a scanning rate of 2° min⁻¹ and microstructural features of fractured surfaces of the sintered compacts were investigated by Scanning Electron Microscopy (Model QUANTA 200, FEI make).

Conclusion :

(i) The minor presence of *in situ* MgCr_2O_4 spinel precursor activates the process of densification of α -alumina system to a great extent and reduces the sintering temperature of α -alumina compacts significantly.

(ii) The addition of an optimum amount (1% w/w) of *in situ* MgCr_2O_4 spinel precursor is highly effective for remarkable improvement in mechanical strength and other physical properties of α -alumina compacts during sintering at temperature as low as 1550 °C.

(iii) *In situ* MgCr_2O_4 spinel as dopant exhibits homogeneous distribution and interlocking of crystalline phases without any grain growth in sintered pure alumina body.

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